

STYLISTIC USE OF INTONATION IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: This thesis examines the impact of intonation on the speaking process, the information delivered, and the situation-appropriate usage of intonation features.

Key words: extralinguistic situation, purpose, subject matters, participants, scene/setting.

It is fact that how crucial it is to give each step in the communication process careful consideration. This is due to the fact that proper intonation when speaking can drastically alter the meaning of the information being communicated, in addition to following grammar rules, word choice, and style. Understanding the idea of intonation, the variables that affect it, and the significance of choosing intonation that complements various speech patterns are crucial in this situation.

Intonation is the part of stylistic, that help us convey the meaning of the oral speech in various situations. In extralinguistic situation we consider age, gender and status of the participants of the communication and make our speech suitable to them.

The uses of intonation in this function show that the information so conveyed is, in many cases, impossible to separate from lexical and grammatical meanings expressed by words and constructions in a language (verbal context) and from the co-occurring situational information (non-verbal context). The meaning of intonation cannot be judged in isolation. However, intonation does not usually correlate in any neat one-for-one way with the verbal context accompanying and the situational variables in an extra-linguistic context. Moreover, the perceived contrast with the intonation of the previous utterance seems to be relevant. In the following example a connecting phrase in the appropriate intonation conditions the stylistic force of the accompanying sentence, and contrasts with the 'literal' meaning of the words:

You 'KNOW | I think he's RIGHT (= let me tell you, I think...)

You KNOW I think he's right (= you are aware that I think...)

One of the objectives of phonostylistics is the study of intonational functional styles. An intonational style can be defined as a system of interrelated intonational means which is used in a certain social sphere and serves a definite aim in communication. The problem of intonational styles classification can hardly be regarded as settled as yet. In this book we distinguish the following five style categories:

- (1) **informational (formal) style;**
- (2) **scientific (academic) style;**
- (3) **declamatory style;**
- (4) **publicistic style;**
- (5) **familiar (conversational) style.**

The situational context and the speaker's purpose determine the choice of an intonational style. The primary situational determinant is the kind of relationship existing between the participants in a communicative transaction.

Intonational styles distinction is based on the assumption that there are three types of information present in communication:

- (a) intellectual information,
- (b) emotional and attitudinal (modal) information,
- (c) volitional and desiderative information.

Consequently, there are **three types of intonation patterns** used in oral communication:

- (a) intonation patterns used for intellectual purposes,
- (b) intonation patterns used for emotional and attitudinal purposes,
- (c) intonation patterns used for volitional and desiderative purposes.

All intonational styles include intellectual intonation patterns, because the aim of any kind of intercourse is to communicate or express some intellectual information. The frequency of occurrence and the overall intonational distribution of emotional (or attitudinal) and volitional (or desiderative) patterns shape the distinctive features of each style.

Informational (formal) style is characterised by the predominant use of intellectual intonation patterns. It occurs in formal discourse where the task set by the sender of the message is to communicate information without giving it any emotional or volitional evaluation. This intonational style is used, for instance, by radio and television announcers when reading weather forecasts, news, etc. or in various official situations. It is considered to be stylistically neutral.

In scientific (academic) style intellectual and volitional (or desiderative) intonation patterns are concurrently employed. The speaker's purpose here is not only to prove a hypothesis, to create new concepts, to disclose relations between different phenomena, etc., but also to direct the listener's attention to the message carried in the semantic component. Although this style tends to be objective and precise, it is not entirely unemotional and devoid of any individuality. Scientific intonational style is frequently used, for example, by university lecturers, school teachers, or by scientists in formal and informal discussions.

In declamatory (artistic) style the emotional role of intonation increases, thereby intonation patterns used for intellectual, volitional (and emotional) purposes have an equal share. The speaker's aim is to appeal simultaneously to the mind, the will and feelings of the listener by image-bearing devices. Declamatory style is generally acquired by special training and it is used, for instance, in stage speech, classroom recitation, verse-speaking or in reading aloud fiction.

Publicistic (oratorical) style is characterized by predominance of volitional (or desiderative) intonation patterns against the background of intellectual and emotional ones. The general aim of this intonational style is to exert influence on the listener, to convince him that the speaker's interpretation is the only correct one and to cause him to accept the point of view expressed in the speech. The task is accomplished not merely through logical argumentation but through persuasion and emotional appeal. For this reason publicistic style has features in common with scientific style, on one hand, and declamatory style, on the other. As distinct from the latter its persuasive and emotional appeal is achieved not by the use of imagery, but in a more direct manner. Publicistic style is made resort to by political speech-makers, radio and television commentators, participants of press conferences and interviews, counsel and judges in courts of law, etc.

The usage of **familiar (conversational) style** is typical of the English. It occurs both within a family group and in informal external relationships, namely, in the speech of intimate friends or well-acquainted people. In such cases it is the emotional reaction to a situational or verbal stimulus that matters, thereby the attitude- and emotion-signalling function of intonation here comes to the fore. Nevertheless intellectual and intonation patterns also have a part to play.

Analysis of most varieties of English speeches shows that the intonational styles in question occur alternately (fusion of styles). For example, a University lecturer can make use of both scientific style (definitions, presentation of scientific facts) and declamatory style (an image-bearing illustration of these definitions and facts).

It should be noted, in conclusion, that a single intonation has a significant impact on communication. Accurate, intelligible, and situationally suitable information transfer from the speaker to the listener facilitates smoother communication while also contributing to the steady development of intercultural communication.

References:

1. Phonetic stylistic methods and methodological application of phraseology in English and Uzbek Rayhona Narziqulova (p 328-329)
2. The importance of the intonation in the stylistic differentiation of oral texts. Modern science and research. Gavkhar Rakhimova. 2(12), 18/21
3. The Intonation as a Stylistic Palette: Insights from Phonostylistic Analysis. Makhliyo Saydaliyeva Ulug'bek qizi (p 45-47)